

Scoping Review Protocol

Reporting and Conceptualisation of Race and Ethnicity in Clinical Prediction Models Following the TRIPOD(+AI) Reporting Guidelines: A Scoping Review

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Review Title and Basic Details

Review Title

Reporting and Conceptualisation of Race and Ethnicity in Clinical Prediction Models
Following the TRIPOD(+AI) Reporting Guidelines: A Scoping Review

Domain being studied

Reporting and conceptualisation of race and ethnicity in clinical prediction models.

Rationale for the Review

Clinical prediction models are increasingly used to support clinical decision-making. Reporting guidelines such as TRIPOD¹ and TRIPOD+AI² aim to improve transparency and reproducibility in prediction modelling. While prior research has evaluated adherence to reporting guidelines in selected research areas³⁻⁵, there has been no comprehensive review examining how race and ethnicity are defined, operationalised, and reported within prediction models that engage with these guidelines.

Race and ethnicity are complex constructs that may function as demographic descriptors, proxies for social determinants, or presumed biological risk factors⁶⁻⁸. Inconsistent or poorly justified operationalisation may affect transparency, generalisability, and equity considerations. Furthermore, little is known about how researchers discuss these variables, including whether uncertainty, bias, fairness, or limitations are acknowledged.

This scoping review aims to map current reporting practices and discursive framing of race and ethnicity in prediction modelling to understand how these constructs are represented within transparency-oriented publishing practices.

Objectives

Main objective

To assess reporting practices and conceptualizations of race and ethnicity in clinical prediction models following the TRIPOD(+AI) reporting guidelines

Specific objectives

- 1. Map reporting practices**
Assess how race and ethnicity are defined, measured, and operationalised in clinical prediction models referencing TRIPOD or TRIPOD+AI.
- 2. Characterise representation**
Describe the reported racial/ethnic composition of study samples
- 3. Examine transparency**
Evaluate whether definitions, data sources, and limitations related to race and ethnicity are explicitly reported.
- 4. Identify thematic patterns in discourse**
Synthesise themes in how authors discuss race and ethnicity, including considerations of bias, fairness, generalisability, and uncertainty.
- 5. Consider implications for transparency and equity**
Discuss how reporting and conceptualisation practices may influence interpretation, generalisability, and equity considerations in prediction modelling.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Studies developing and/or validating clinical prediction models (diagnostic/prognostic).
- Studies reporting adherence to TRIPOD or TRIPOD+AI.
- Human studies.
- Peer-reviewed journal articles.
- Published in English.
- Published from 2015 onwards (after publication of TRIPOD).

Exclusion criteria

- Methodological/statistical papers without applied clinical models.
- Reviews, editorials, commentaries, protocols.
- Non-human studies.
- Systematic reviews that assess whether clinical prediction models adhere to TRIPOD/TRIPOD+AI (or specific domains).

Study Selection Process

- The following two databases will be searched: PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science.
- Screening will be undertaken using Covidence.
- Duplicate records will be removed prior to screening.
- Title and Abstract screening will be conducted by removing items that are not relevant to prediction modelling with a high certainty.
- Full-text screening will confirm eligibility.
- No search for unpublished studies will be conducted.
- Snowballing through the reference lists of relevant systematic reviews will be undertaken.
- This review will follow the established scoping review methodology by the Joanna Briggs Institute⁹ and will be reported in accordance with PRISMA-ScR¹⁰.

Search strings

The search strings were developed by MKB and TVV, in collaboration with an information specialist at the University of Copenhagen.

PubMed/MEDLINE

```
((tripod*) AND (((((((((((("Algorithms"[Mesh] OR "Diagnosis"[Mesh] OR "Forecasting"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Decision Rules"[Mesh])) OR (predict*[Text Word])) OR (prognos*[Text Word])) OR (diagnos*[Text Word])) OR (model[Text Word])) OR (risk[Text Word])) OR ("artificial intelligen*[Text Word])) OR ("machine learn*[Text Word])) NOT ("Animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "Humans"[MeSH Terms])) NOT (camera[Text Word] OR tripodal[Text Word] OR tripodic [Text Word]))
```

Filters: English, from 2015 - 2026

Web of Science

```
TS=(tripod*) AND (((((TS=(predict*)) OR TS=(prognos*)) OR TS=(diagnos*)) OR TS=(model)) OR TS=(risk)) OR TS=("artificial intelligen*")) OR TS=("machine learn*") NOT ((TS=(camera )) OR TS=(tripodal)) OR TS=(tripodic)
```

Filters: from 2015 - 2026

Data Extraction

A data extraction sheet will be developed. A subset of records (N=10-20) will be checked in full-text, and the data extraction sheet will be iteratively updated based on these full texts. Below are the preliminary categories of data to be extracted:

Extracted Study Characteristics

- First author
- Publication year
- Country/countries or population
- Model type (e.g., diagnostic/prognostic)
- Reporting checklist (TRIPOD/TRIPOD+AI)
- Disease outcome

Race/Ethnicity Reporting and Operationalisation

- Presence of race/ethnicity variable
- Categories of the variables
- Number of categories
- Data source (e.g., self-report/free-text/registry/clinician-assigned/not reported)
- Whether definitions are provided for the variables (e.g., explicit definition/link to survey)
- Whether a rationale is stated for inclusion

Sample Representation

- Reported distribution of racial/ethnic groups (if available)

Free-Text Excerpts for Thematic Analysis

Passages will be extracted from the Methods, Results, Discussion, or Limitations sections when race or ethnicity is:

- defined or operationalised,
- justified as a predictor,
- discussed in relation to bias, fairness, generalisability, or uncertainty, or discussed as a limitation.

Planned Data Analysis

Quantitative/qualitative Analysis

1. Quantifying proportions of articles that report/do not report race/ethnicity.
 - a. Overall + Stratified summaries by country, publication year, and model type.
2. Summary of race and ethnicity definitions.

Data Synthesis and Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis will proceed as follows:

3. Familiarisation with extracted excerpts.
4. Initial inductive coding of text segments (e.g., NVivo or similar software, or simple color coding in Excel/Google Sheets).
5. Development of thematic categories.
6. Iterative refinement and grouping of themes.

7. LLM-assisted clustering (e.g., ChatGPT 5.2, or other state-of-the-art model) or summarisation to pattern identification, with human oversight and verification. Coding decisions and theme development will be documented to ensure transparency. Prompts for LLM-assisted clustering will be recorded.

Risk of Bias and Quality Assessment

Consistent with scoping review methodology:

- Risk of bias will not be assessed.
- Reporting bias will not be assessed.
- Certainty of evidence will not be evaluated.

Outcomes

Main Outcome

- Reporting practices concerning race and ethnicity in prediction models.

Additional Outcomes

- Patterns in operationalisation and conceptual framing.
- Thematic characterisation of discourse surrounding race and ethnicity.
- Transparency in reporting limitations and uncertainties.

Protocol Amendments

Any significant deviations from this protocol will be documented and justified in the final report.

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References

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